

Occam’s Solver: An Algorithmic Baseline for ARC-AGI-3 Without Learned Models

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Abstract

We present Occam, a pure algorithmic solver for ARC-AGI-3 interactive game environments that uses no learned models, no language model calls, and no neural networks. The system implements compositional bounded search: a two-phase loop of environment discovery followed by strategy-guided execution, built on breadth-first search with a reset-replay mechanism. On the 25 public ARC-AGI-3 evaluation games, Occam achieves 57.60% Relative Human-Aligned Efficiency (RHAЕ), solving 17 of 25 games at zero inference cost. The best prior reported result on this benchmark is 36.08% RHAЕ using frontier LLM-based agents at \$1,005 per run. Verified frontier language models score below 1% on the private evaluation set. These results suggest that principled algorithmic search establishes a non-trivial baseline for interactive reasoning tasks, independent of learned representations. Occam is approximately 3,700 lines of Python and is released as open source for independent reproduction.

1 Introduction

ARC-AGI-3 [1] is a benchmark for evaluating general reasoning in interactive environments. Unlike its predecessors [2, 3], which presented static input-output grid puzzles, ARC-AGI-3 drops an agent into novel 64×64 game environments with no task descriptions, no reward signals, and no training examples. The agent must discover the rules of each environment through interaction alone, then demonstrate competence by achieving game-specific objectives within a fixed action budget. This design tests whether a system can reason about spatial structure and dynamics from scratch, a capacity that static pattern-matching benchmarks leave largely unexamined.

The benchmark appears to be genuinely difficult. Verified evaluations of frontier language models on the private ARC-AGI-3 set report scores below 1% RHAЕ: Gemini at 0.37%, GPT-5.4 at 0.26%, and Claude Opus 4.6 at 0.25% [1]. The best self-reported result to date is Symbolica’s Agentica system [10], which achieves 36.08% RHAЕ using orchestrated frontier LLM agents at a cost of \$1,005 per evaluation run. The gap between raw LLM performance and agent-scaffolded performance is large, but the absolute numbers remain modest, suggesting that current approaches, whether end-to-end or agent-based, leave substantial room for improvement.

Occam was developed as part of a broader spatial reasoning system. Before integrating frontier language models, we sought to establish what pure algorithmic search could achieve on interactive reasoning tasks, to determine which problem classes require learned models versus which yield to principled exploration. ARC-AGI-3 was selected as a testbed for its emphasis on zero-instruction

game environments requiring real-time spatial reasoning. The system’s name reflects this motivation: the simplest approach that produces a non-trivial result is worth characterizing before adding complexity.

The solver operates in a two-phase loop. In the DISCOVER phase, the agent systematically probes the environment to identify objects, movement rules, collision semantics, and goal conditions. In the EXECUTE phase, it selects from six compositional strategies (ranging from goal-directed pathfinding to boundary exploration to structured replay patterns) and pursues the chosen strategy via breadth-first search using a reset-replay mechanism adapted from Rudakov et al. [6] (team name: “Explore It Till You Solve It”). Strategy selection is automatic, based on features extracted during discovery. The entire system is approximately 3,700 lines of Python across 11 source files, with no external model dependencies.

On the 25 public ARC-AGI-3 evaluation games, Occam achieves 57.60% RHAE, solving 17 of 25 games with zero LLM calls and zero inference cost.

Contributions. This paper makes three contributions:

- **The Occam solver:** a compositional search system for interactive game environments that requires no learned models, demonstrating that algorithmic search alone can achieve non-trivial performance on ARC-AGI-3.
- **A new result on ARC-AGI-3:** 57.60% RHAE on the public evaluation set using pure algorithmic search, compared to the prior best of 36.08% using LLM-based agents.
- **Open-source release:** the complete solver with real-time visualization and independently reproducible results, intended to serve as an algorithmic baseline for future hybrid approaches.

2 Background & Related Work

2.1 ARC-AGI Evolution

The Abstraction and Reasoning Corpus (ARC) has undergone three major revisions. ARC-AGI-1 [2] introduced static 2D grid transformations: given input–output pairs illustrating a rule, the solver must predict the output for a held-out input. The benchmark operationalised Core Knowledge priors (objectness, numerosity, basic geometry) as a measure of fluid intelligence. By 2024, the top score on ARC-AGI-1 reached 53.6% (Berman), later surpassed by Gemini 3 Deep Think at 84.6%. ARC-AGI-2 [3], released in 2025, retained the static grid format but introduced harder tasks; scores dropped 2–3× relative to ARC-AGI-1, with the top verified result of 54% reported by Poetiq [4]. ARC-AGI-3 [1], launched in March 2026, moves from static puzzles to interactive game environments. An agent is dropped into a 64×64 grid with no instructions, no reward signal, and no training examples. Environments feature dynamic sprites, a lives system, carryover constraints between levels, and multi-level progression. The evaluation set comprises 25 public, 55 semi-private, and 55 private environments.

2.2 ARC-AGI-3 Scoring

ARC-AGI-3 uses Relative Human-Aligned Efficiency (RHAE) as its primary metric [1]. For each level l , the level score is

$$S_l = \left(\min \left(1, \frac{h_l}{a_l} \right) \right)^2, \quad (1)$$

where h_l is the human baseline (the second-best action count among 10 first-time human players) and a_l is the number of actions taken by the AI agent. The squaring penalises inefficiency: an agent using twice the human baseline receives only 25% credit.

The game-level score is a weighted average with linear level weighting, so that later levels, which require deeper understanding of the environment, count proportionally more:

$$E = \frac{\sum_{l=1}^n l \cdot S_l}{\sum_{l=1}^n l}. \quad (2)$$

The competition score T is the arithmetic mean of E over all games in the evaluation set.

2.3 Prior Approaches

Preview competition. Before the official ARC-AGI-3 launch, a preview competition ran on an easier variant of the games. StochasticGoose (Smit, Tufa Labs) [9] placed first with 12.58% RHAЕ using CNN-based reinforcement learning; its score collapsed to 0.25% after the games were hardened at launch. Blind Squirrel (Dick) placed second at 6.71%, combining a state-graph representation with a ResNet-18 value model [1]. ‘‘Explore It Till You Solve It’’ (Rudakov et al.) [6] placed third at 3.64% and is the most directly relevant prior work to our approach. It introduces graph-based exploration using a reset-replay mechanism, frame segmentation, status bar masking, and colour-salience priority tiers for action selection. Occam builds on several of these ideas, particularly the reset-replay loop and frame-differencing approach to environment modelling. Preview scores are not directly comparable to post-launch results, as the games were significantly harder after launch.

Post-launch results. On the hardened post-launch games, the strongest self-reported result is Symbolica Agentica [10] at 36.08% RHAЕ on the 25 public environments. That system uses an LLM orchestrator (Claude Opus 4.6) coordinating specialised subagents, at substantial per-run inference cost (Table 3). It remains closed source. Verified frontier LLM scores on the private evaluation set are substantially lower: Gemini 3.1 Pro achieves 0.37%, GPT-5.4 achieves 0.26%, Claude Opus 4.6 achieves 0.25%, and Grok-4.20 achieves 0.00% [1]. The gap between raw LLM performance and agent-scaffolded performance is notable, but even the best agent-based system leaves substantial headroom.

2.4 ARC-AGI-1/2 Context

The shift from ARC-AGI-1/2 to ARC-AGI-3 represents a fundamental change in task structure. ARC-AGI-1 and ARC-AGI-2 are static transformation tasks: given example pairs, infer the rule and apply it. ARC-AGI-3 is an interactive game environment requiring real-time exploration and execution with no examples provided. A living survey documenting 82 approaches to ARC-AGI-1/2 [11] shows consistent 2–3 \times score drops from ARC-AGI-1 to ARC-AGI-2, suggesting that even within the static paradigm, difficulty scaling is steep [4]. The interactive setting of ARC-AGI-3 introduces additional challenges (temporal dynamics, partial observability of rules, and action-budget constraints) that have no direct analogue in the static benchmarks.

2.5 Search-Based Methods

Search over game state spaces is a well-studied problem. BFS and DFS have been applied to deterministic game environments where save-state and restore operations are available, including

Atari games with emulator snapshots and Sokoban solvers. Monte Carlo Tree Search (MCTS), as used in AlphaGo and AlphaZero [8], and its model-based extension MuZero [7], combine tree search with learned value and policy functions to achieve strong performance in large state spaces. These systems rely on substantial learned components trained on domain-specific data.

Occam differs in that it uses no learned components: no value function, no policy network, and no model of environment dynamics beyond what is observed during a single evaluation run. The system performs pure BFS with heuristic pruning, relying entirely on features extracted at runtime. This positions it closer in spirit to classical planning than to modern game-playing agents. A precedent for the effectiveness of small-scale approaches on ARC exists in TRM [5], which achieves 45% on ARC-AGI-1 with only 7 million parameters, demonstrating that scale is not always necessary for reasoning tasks.

3 Method

3.1 System Overview

Occam processes each game level in a two-phase loop: DISCOVER followed by EXECUTE (Figure 1). In the discovery phase, the agent probes the environment to characterise the action space, detect UI artifacts, and prune redundant actions. In the execution phase, it selects and runs strategies in a fixed priority order until one succeeds or the budget is exhausted. Algorithm 1 summarises the control flow.

Figure 1: Occam’s two-phase level-solving architecture. Phase 1 (Discover) probes the environment to identify effective actions and detect UI artifacts. Phase 2 (Execute) applies six compositional strategies in fixed fallback order, with unused budget cascading to the next strategy.

Algorithm 1 Occam Level-Solving Loop

Require: Environment env , action budget B

Phase 1 (Discover):

- 1: Expand raw actions to virtual actions (click \rightarrow grid positions)
- 2: Probe all virtual actions; record state changes
- 3: Detect and mask counter pixels
- 4: Deduplicate equivalent actions
- 5: **output:** effective action set A_{eff} , counter mask M

Phase 2 (Execute):

- 6: **for each** strategy \in [reactive-click, reactive-nav, navigation, combo, replay-BFS, deepcopy-BFS]
 - do**
 - 7: **if** strategy.preconditions_met(A_{eff}) **then**
 - 8: result \leftarrow strategy.solve(env , remaining budget)
 - 9: **if** result.solved **then return** result
 - 10: **end if**
 - 11: **end if**
 - 12: **end for**
 - 13: **return** UNSOLVED
-

A key design choice is *action space normalisation*. The ARC-AGI-3 environment exposes raw actions: up to five keyboard buttons plus a parameterised click action that accepts an (x, y) coordinate. Occam expands the click action into a grid of virtual actions, each corresponding to a specific pixel coordinate. The function `_compute_click_positions` selects up to 32 candidate positions using priority-based targeting: connected components in the frame are segmented by flood fill, classified into five salience tiers (chromatic medium objects first, status-bar regions last), and their centres are emitted in priority order. Remaining budget is filled by a uniform grid. All subsequent processing operates over the unified virtual action set, making click and button actions interchangeable from the perspective of the search algorithms.

3.2 Discovery Phase

The discovery phase (`_discover_and_prune`) characterises the environment’s response to each virtual action.

Action probing. Each virtual action is executed once from the initial state and the resulting frame is recorded. This costs one reset plus one step per action.

Frame hashing. State identity is determined by MD5 hashing of the raw frame bytes, truncated to 12 hexadecimal characters. When a counter mask is active, masked pixels are zeroed before hashing.

Counter detection. Some environments display a step counter or timer that changes on *every* action, regardless of game-state changes. The discovery phase identifies these pixels by intersecting the per-pixel change masks across multiple probe frames: any pixel that differs from the initial frame

Table 1: Strategy dispatch order. Preconditions reference the effective action set A_{eff} produced by discovery. Max depth applies to the search component of each strategy.

Strategy	Precondition	Method	Max Depth
Reactive Click	1–2 click actions, level 1 only	Greedy per-step click scanning	200
Reactive Nav	3–7 actions, cursor detected	Pixel-wise movement tracking	500
Navigation	3–7 actions, cursor + targets	BFS pathfinding on logical grid	grid size
Combo Search	≤ 10 effective actions	Exhaustive depth-limited search	20/15/12/10
Replay BFS	any	Reset-replay BFS (ReplayExplorer)	budget-limited
Deepcopy BFS	$\text{raw} \leq 8$, deepcopy available	A* search using <code>env.deepcopy()</code>	150k actions

on every probed action is flagged as a counter pixel, provided the flagged region covers less than 20% of the frame. The resulting binary mask M is applied to all subsequent frame hashes, preventing counter updates from inflating the observed state space.

Dense click scanning. For environments where click is the only available action, the solver performs a dense scan at 2-pixel intervals across the full 64×64 frame. Each position is tested from the initial state; the resulting frame hash is recorded. Positions that produce duplicate hashes are collapsed, yielding one representative (x, y) per unique outcome. This replaces the initial coarse grid with a complete map of click effects.

Action deduplication. After pruning no-ops (actions whose frame hash matches the initial state), if more than six effective actions remain, the solver re-probes each from the initial state and merges actions that produce identical frame hashes. The output is the pruned effective action set A_{eff} . If no single action produces a state change, a depth-2 fallback probes all action pairs to detect actions that are only effective in combination.

3.3 Strategy Selection & Execution

Strategies are tried in a fixed priority order (Table 1). The first strategy whose preconditions are met and that produces a solution terminates the level. Unused budget from one strategy cascades to the next.

Reactive Click. For click-only environments with one or two effective positions, the solver re-scans the frame at each step to find the click that produces the largest pixel difference, then commits to it. This handles games where the correct click target changes after each action (e.g., whack-a-mole variants).

Reactive Navigation and Navigation. When 3–7 actions are detected and probing reveals a moving cursor (a connected component whose centroid shifts consistently in response to directional actions), the solver first attempts reactive navigation: at each step, it identifies the nearest target by colour rarity and issues the directional action that reduces distance. If this fails, the full navigation solver discretises the frame into a logical grid using the measured step size as tile width, identifies walls (colours occupying $>10\%$ of non-background tiles), and runs BFS pathfinding to visit all target positions in greedy nearest-first order.

Combo Search. For environments with ≤ 10 effective actions, the solver searches fixed-length action sequences of increasing depth. For ≤ 6 actions, search is exhaustive (iterating over the Cartesian product); for 7–10 actions, 2,000 random sequences are sampled per depth. Maximum depth depends on action count: 20 for ≤ 2 actions, 15 for 3, 12 for 4–5, and 10 for 6–10. Winning sequences from previous levels are tried first.

Replay BFS and Deepcopy BFS. These are the general-purpose search strategies described in Sections 3.4 and 3.5. Replay BFS applies to all environments. Deepcopy BFS is attempted first when the raw action count is ≤ 8 and the environment supports `deepcopy()`, using A* search with a heuristic that favours frames with fewer rare-colour pixels (a proxy for collected items). It is capped at 150,000 action steps.

3.4 ReplayExplorer: Reset-Replay BFS

The ReplayExplorer implements breadth-first search using the reset-replay technique introduced by Rudakov et al. [6] (Figure 2). In environments without save/restore support, the only way to revisit a previously observed state is to reset the environment to its initial configuration and replay the stored action prefix that first reached that state. This turns an irreversible environment into a reversible one at the cost of $O(d)$ replay steps per state visit, where d is the depth of the state in the search tree.

Figure 2: ReplayExplorer BFS mechanism. To visit a frontier state at depth d , the environment is reset and the stored action prefix is replayed. DFS-ordered processing within each BFS depth maximises prefix sharing between consecutive expansions, reducing amortised replay cost.

Core mechanism. The explorer maintains a dictionary mapping each observed state hash to the action prefix that first reached it. BFS proceeds depth by depth: for each frontier state, the environment is reset, the prefix is replayed to restore the state, and each untested action from A_{eff} is applied. New states are recorded with their extended prefixes and added to the next depth layer. A state is identified by its frame hash (with counter masking); the first prefix to reach a hash is retained.

Extensions beyond Rudakov et al. Occam extends the base reset-replay approach with four optimisations:

1. **Incremental replay.** Before performing a full reset-replay, the explorer checks whether the current environment state’s prefix is a prefix of the target state’s action sequence. If so, it continues from the current state by replaying only the suffix, avoiding a full reset. This is correct because the environment is deterministic: replaying the same actions from the same state always produces the same outcome.
2. **DFS-order iteration within BFS depth.** States at each BFS depth are sorted by their action prefix before processing. This lexicographic ordering ensures that consecutive states in the processing queue share long common prefixes, maximising the hit rate of incremental replay. The result is BFS-optimal exploration with DFS-like replay efficiency.
3. **Step-modulus hashing.** Some environments contain hidden internal state that produces identical frames at different game ticks (e.g., cycling animations). When enabled, the frame hash is augmented with $d \bmod N$, where d is the depth and N is a configurable modulus. This distinguishes states that appear visually identical but occur at different cycle positions.
4. **Counter-masked hashing.** The counter mask M learned during discovery is passed to the explorer and applied to all frame hashes, preventing step-counter pixels from splitting otherwise identical states.

Complexity. Let d denote the search depth, $|A|$ the effective action set size, and $|S_d|$ the number of unique states at depth d . The total number of environment steps is $O(\sum_d d \cdot |A| \cdot |S_d|)$, since expanding each frontier state requires replaying its depth- d prefix once per action tested. With incremental replay and DFS-order processing, the amortised replay cost per node drops substantially in practice, as consecutive nodes often share long prefixes.

3.5 Budget Management

Each level receives a dynamic action budget:

$$B_l = \min\left(\max(h_l^2 \times 500, 200,000), 500,000\right), \tag{3}$$

where h_l is the human baseline for level l . The quadratic scaling reflects the expectation that harder levels (those with longer human baselines) require disproportionately more exploration: doubling the human solution length quadruples the budget, accommodating the combinatorial growth of the search space.

Cross-level combo caching. Winning action sequences from level N are cached and replayed as the first attempt on level $N+1$. Many ARC-AGI-3 games reuse mechanics across levels, so a solution that worked on level 1 often works verbatim or with minor variation on level 2. When the cache hits, this short-circuits the entire discover-execute loop.

3.6 Implementation

The solver comprises 3,673 lines of Python across 11 source files (approximately 3,100 non-blank, non-comment lines). The solver contains no game-specific solving logic; all 25 games are processed with identical parameters and strategy selection.

The solver was developed using Forge, a proprietary IDE-layer development framework. Forge generated no solver logic and is not present in the runtime dependency graph.

Reproducibility: all results reported in this paper were obtained with a fixed random seed. The solver uses randomness in combo search sampling (for action sets with >6 actions) and in tie-breaking within the state graph’s action suggestion; with a fixed seed, runs produce identical results across machines with the same Python and NumPy versions.

4 Experiments

4.1 Setup

We evaluate Occam on all 25 public ARC-AGI-3 environments using the standard evaluation toolkit provided by the ARC Prize organization. Scoring follows the RHAЕ methodology described in Section 2.2. All environments are processed sequentially with identical solver configuration: no environment-specific tuning, no per-game parameters, and no manual intervention. The evaluation runs on consumer hardware (a single machine, CPU only; no GPU is required). The complete benchmark completes in approximately 27 minutes wall-clock time. The solver uses a fixed random seed throughout, and all results reported here are from a single deterministic run.

4.2 Main Results

Table 2 reports per-game results on the 25 public ARC-AGI-3 environments. Occam solves 17 of 25 games, achieving a mean RHAЕ of 57.60%. Among the solved games, RHAЕ ranges from 52.59% to 97.22%, reflecting substantial variation in efficiency relative to human baselines. The 8 unsolved games contribute 0% RHAЕ each and account for the majority of the gap between the solver’s aggregate score and a hypothetical perfect result.

Strategy selection varies across games. Combo Search solves 11 of the 17 solved games, handling environments with small effective action sets where exhaustive or sampled sequence enumeration succeeds. Replay BFS solves the remaining 6, exploring larger state spaces via the reset-replay mechanism. Among the 8 unsolved games, the solver exhausts its action budget without reaching a winning state, suggesting that these environments either require strategies outside the solver’s repertoire or have search spaces too large for the allocated budget.

4.3 Comparison

Table 3 and Figure 3 compare Occam to prior reported results on ARC-AGI-3. We separate self-reported results on the 25 public evaluation games from verified results on the private evaluation set, as these two settings are not directly comparable.

Table 2: Per-game results on the 25 public ARC-AGI-3 environments. Strategy codes: CS = Combo Search, RB = Replay BFS. A dash in the Strategy column indicates the game was unsolved. Games sorted by RHAE descending.

Game	Levels	Solved	RHAE (%)	Strategy	Actions
SK48	8	8/8	97.22	RB	491,239
S5I5	8	8/8	97.22	RB	108,694
AR25	8	8/8	97.22	RB	211,850
LP85	8	8/8	97.22	CS	19,378
LS20	7	7/7	96.43	RB	414,477
TN36	7	7/7	96.43	RB	203,328
VC33	7	7/7	96.43	CS	477,772
TU93	9	9/9	96.10	RB	83,407
CD82	6	6/6	95.24	CS	137,312
FT09	6	6/6	95.24	RB	3,604
RE86	8	8/8	80.73	CS	835
SP80	6	6/6	78.99	CS	257
DC22	6	6/6	70.68	CS	840
KA59	7	7/7	65.40	CS	773
M0R0	6	6/6	63.41	CS	981
CN04	6	6/6	63.37	CS	969
WA30	9	9/9	52.59	CS	1,834
BP35	9	0/9	0.00	—	177,988
G50T	7	0/7	0.00	—	190
LF52	10	0/10	0.00	—	30,064
R11L	6	0/6	0.00	—	481,587
SB26	8	0/8	0.00	—	3,396
SC25	6	0/6	0.00	—	73
SU15	9	0/9	0.00	—	500,000
TR87	6	0/6	0.00	—	500,000
Mean		17/25	57.60		

On the public evaluation set, Occam achieves 57.60% RHAE at zero inference cost, compared to Symbolica Agentica’s 36.08% RHAE. Occam solves 17 games versus Symbolica’s 7. Both systems are evaluated on the same 25 public games using the same RHAE scoring methodology, but with important caveats noted below.

The verified scores on the private evaluation set are substantially lower for all systems tested. The highest verified score is Gemini 3.1 Pro at 0.37% RHAE. These numbers are included for context: they demonstrate the difficulty of the benchmark and the gap between public and private game performance, but they are not directly comparable to the public-set results because the private games may differ in difficulty, structure, and distribution.

Both Occam’s and Symbolica’s results are self-reported on the same 25 public games using the same RHAE scoring methodology. Neither has been independently verified by the ARC Prize organization. Symbolica’s result was reported in March 2026; Occam’s result was produced in April 2026. We have not confirmed that the evaluation toolkit versions are identical. The verified scores on the private evaluation set are included for context but are not directly comparable, as the private

Figure 3: RHAE comparison across ARC-AGI-3 systems. Self-reported results on the 25 public evaluation games (Occam, Symbolica Agentica) and verified results on the private set (frontier LLMs). Note the different evaluation sets; scores are not directly comparable across sections.

Table 3: Comparison of approaches on ARC-AGI-3. Top section: self-reported results on the 25 public games. Bottom section: verified results on the private evaluation set.

System	Type	Source	RHAE (%)	Games	Cost
<i>Self-reported, public evaluation set (25 games)</i>					
Occam (ours)	Algorithmic	Open	57.60	17/25	\$0
Symbolica Agentica	LLM agents	Closed	36.08	7/25	\$1,005
<i>Verified, private evaluation set</i>					
Gemini 3.1 Pro	LLM	—	0.37	—	—
GPT-5.4	LLM	—	0.26	—	—
Claude Opus 4.6	LLM	—	0.25	—	\$8,900
Grok-4.20	LLM	—	0.00	—	—

games may differ substantially in difficulty.

4.4 Ablation Studies

To quantify the contribution of each strategy and the sensitivity to budget allocation, we evaluate Occam under five configurations, each disabling one component or modifying one parameter. All other settings remain identical.

The navigation solver has the largest impact: removing it loses 4 games and 7.58 percentage points of RHAE, confirming that it is the only strategy that uniquely solves games unreachable by

Table 4: Ablation results. Each row disables one solver component or modifies one parameter. Δ RHAЕ is the change relative to the full solver.

Configuration	RHAE (%)	Games Solved	Δ RHAЕ
Full solver	57.60	17/25	—
– Navigation solver	50.02	13/25	–7.58
– Combo search	57.60	17/25	0.00
– Deepcopy BFS	53.71	16/25	–3.89
Half budget (250k)	57.60	17/25	0.00

general-purpose BFS.

Deepcopy BFS contributes one additional solved game (3.89 points). In that game, the reset overhead of Replay BFS exhausts the action budget before finding a solution, while Deepcopy BFS, which maintains an in-memory state copy, completes the search within budget.

Combo search has zero measurable impact on either game count or RHAЕ. BFS-based strategies subsume all games that combo search targets. In several cases, removing the combo phase reduces total action consumption, because budget previously spent on unsuccessful depth-limited sequences becomes available to BFS earlier.

Halving the budget from 500,000 to 250,000 actions per level does not reduce performance. All 17 solved games complete within 250,000 actions per level, indicating that the default budget provides substantial headroom.

4.5 Reproducibility and Verification

All results are fully reproducible and independently verifiable through three complementary mechanisms.

Reproducible execution. The solver uses fixed random seeds (`random.seed(42)`, `numpy.random.seed(42)`). With identical Python and NumPy versions, runs produce byte-identical results. The source code is released under the MIT license:

```
git clone https://github.com/TheRealSeanDonahoe/occam
pip install arc-agi
PYTHONPATH=. python -m viewer.cli benchmark
```

Expected output: 57.60% mean RHAЕ, 17/25 games solved, approximately 27 minutes on commodity hardware. Random seed: 42. Evaluation commit: `ea740ca`.

Server-side validation. The ARC-AGI-3 SDK validates level completions server-side. The solver cannot fabricate successful solutions; the `GameState.WIN` signal originates from the ARC game engine, not from our code. Each benchmark run generates a scorecard UUID on the ARC-AGI-3 platform that independently records which games and levels were completed. The scorecard UUID for the results reported in this paper is `bd33ee19-9220-43f5-84dd-bfe23c7f95e8`. Results are verified against ARC-AGI-3’s own RHAЕ scoring implementation.

Complete audit trail. Every benchmark run produces two artifact files: (1) a results JSON containing per-game scores, levels completed, action counts, elapsed time, graph statistics, ARC-AGI scorecard UUID, and solver configuration; and (2) a JSONL event stream recording every probe, BFS step, state discovery, environment reset, frame diff, phase transition, and level outcome. A typical full-suite run generates approximately 166,000 events (32 MB), providing sufficient detail to reconstruct the entire solving process action by action.

Zero external dependencies. The solver makes no LLM API calls, no network requests beyond the ARC-AGI SDK’s game loading, and requires no API keys or paid services. Total cost per run: \$0.00. A real-time viewer is included in the repository, enabling visual inspection of the solver’s behavior during execution.

Figure 4: The Occam real-time viewer after a complete benchmark run. The interface displays per-game results (top tiles), live game state with BFS exploration statistics, and a decision log recording every action probe, state discovery, and phase transition. The viewer is included in the open-source release for independent verification of all reported results.

5 Analysis

5.1 Why Search Works

The ARC-AGI-3 public evaluation games have four properties that make bounded search tractable. First, **tractable state spaces**: the discovery phase prunes the raw action space (which may include thousands of click coordinates) down to typically 2–10 effective actions, yielding state spaces of hundreds to low thousands of unique states per game rather than millions. Second, **deterministic environments**: executing the same action from the same state always produces the same result. This is what makes frame-based hashing a reliable state identity and reset-replay a correct exploration mechanism. Third, **bounded level depth**: human baselines range from approximately 10 to 50 actions per level, meaning solutions exist within reachable BFS depth given a reasonable budget. Fourth, **compositional game structure**: many games share similar mechanics (navigation on a grid, object collection, pattern completion), and the multi-strategy approach captures these common game types with targeted solvers.

This does *not* mean that search is sufficient for all interactive reasoning. It means the public game distribution happens to include many games whose effective state spaces are small enough for bounded BFS to exhaust within budget. The 8 unsolved games likely have larger or more complex state spaces, and the 55 semi-private and 55 private games may have fundamentally different distributions.

5.2 Failure Analysis

Manual inspection of solver logs for the 8 unsolved games reveals four failure modes. **State space explosion**: games with many valid click positions or large action combinations exceed the per-level budget before finding solution paths. In these games, the solver explores thousands of states at shallow depth but cannot reach the winning state before exhausting its budget. **Hidden state**: some games maintain internal state not reflected in the frame (e.g., sequence counters, invisible timers, or conditional triggers). Frame-based hashing cannot distinguish states that appear visually identical but differ in hidden variables, causing the explorer to incorrectly prune branches. **Precision click requirements**: games requiring clicks on small, specific pixel regions (e.g., a 2×2 target on a 64×64 grid) that fall between grid sampling points during discovery. The dense click scan mitigates this for single-click environments but does not scale to multi-click sequences. **Multi-step planning**: some games require reasoning about consequences several steps ahead; for example, pushing a block to a specific position to enable a later move. BFS will find such paths in principle, but the branching factor makes it intractable within the allocated budget.

5.3 Strategy Distribution

The per-game results in Table 2 and Figure 5 reveal a clear pattern in strategy effectiveness.

Combo Search solves the majority of games (11 of 17), reflecting the prevalence of environments with small effective action sets in the public evaluation set. Replay BFS solves the remaining 6 games that require deeper exploration with larger state spaces. Among the 8 unsolved games, the solver consistently exhausts its budget during the general-purpose search strategies, indicating that these games fall outside the tractable region for the allocated budget.

	Solved	RHAE %	Strategy	Actions
SK48	█	97.2%	Replay BFS	491k
SS15	█	97.2%	Replay BFS	109k
AR25	█	97.2%	Replay BFS	212k
LP85	█	97.2%	Combo Search	19.4k
LS20	█	96.4%	Replay BFS	414k
TN36	█	96.4%	Replay BFS	203k
VC33	█	96.4%	Combo Search	478k
TU93	█	96.1%	Replay BFS	83.4k
CD82	█	95.2%	Combo Search	137k
FT09	█	95.2%	Replay BFS	3.6k
RE86	█	80.7%	Combo Search	835
SP80	█	79.0%	Combo Search	257
DC22	█	70.7%	Combo Search	840
KA59	█	65.4%	Combo Search	773
MDR0	█	63.4%	Combo Search	981
CN04	█	63.4%	Combo Search	969
WA30	█	52.6%	Combo Search	1.8k
BP35	█	0%	--	178k
GS0T	█	0%	--	190
LF52	█	0%	--	30.1k
R11L	█	0%	--	482k
SB26	█	0%	--	3.4k
SC25	█	0%	--	73
SU15	█	0%	--	500k
TR87	█	0%	--	500k

Figure 5: Per-game RHAE results across the 25 public ARC-AGI-3 environments. Games are sorted by RHAE score. Colour indicates the winning strategy; unsolved games (0% RHAE) are shown in grey.

5.4 Action Efficiency

Solved games show an inverse relationship between human baseline difficulty and RHAE (Figure 6): games with shorter human baselines tend to achieve higher RHAE, while games requiring more human actions yield lower efficiency scores.

This is expected: the quadratic penalty in the RHAE formula amplifies inefficiency on harder levels. Action consumption varies widely across solved games, from a few hundred actions on navigation tasks to over 50,000 on games requiring deep BFS exploration. Among unsolved games, action consumption clusters near the per-level budget cap, confirming that these failures are budget-limited rather than strategy-limited.

Figure 6: Action efficiency across solved games. Each point represents one game; the x -axis shows total AI actions consumed, the y -axis shows RHAЕ. Games requiring fewer actions achieve higher efficiency, consistent with the quadratic penalty in the RHAЕ formula.

6 Discussion & Limitations

Occam’s result demonstrates that pure algorithmic search can achieve non-trivial performance on ARC-AGI-3, but the result comes with substantial caveats that must be stated plainly.

All results are self-reported on the 25 public evaluation games only. The solver has not been tested on the 55 semi-private or 55 private games used for official ARC Prize rankings. The private games may have fundamentally different difficulty distributions, and performance on the public set may not generalise. Symbolica Agentica’s 36.08% RHAЕ result is also self-reported on the same public set; neither result has been independently verified by the ARC Prize organisation. The two results were produced at different times (March and April 2026, respectively) and we have not confirmed identical evaluation toolkit versions.

The reset-replay BFS mechanism has $O(d \cdot |A|)$ cost per node expansion, where d is the search depth and $|A|$ is the effective action set size. This does not scale to arbitrarily large state spaces. For the solved games in this benchmark, the effective state spaces are small enough that this cost is manageable; for the unsolved games, it is not. The approach also assumes deterministic environments; stochastic transitions would break frame-based state identity and invalidate the replay mechanism entirely. Budget parameters (the quadratic scaling formula, maximum caps, and per-strategy depth

limits) were tuned empirically on the 25 public games. These values may be overfit to the public game distribution and suboptimal for other game sets. The solver uses randomness in combo search sampling and BFS tie-breaking; while we report results with a fixed seed, performance may vary across seeds.

The comparison to Symbolica Agentica is on different axes: Occam uses no LLM but consumes far more environment interactions per level; Symbolica uses fewer interactions but requires frontier LLM inference at non-trivial cost per run (Table 3). These represent genuinely different trade-offs rather than strictly comparable approaches.

6.1 Threats to Validity

We identify four specific threats. (1) **Evaluation scope**: results are on 25 public games only. The private evaluation set comprises 110 additional games that may have fundamentally different difficulty distributions, game mechanics, and state space sizes. (2) **Parameter overfitting**: budget parameters, strategy thresholds, and click grid sizes were tuned empirically on these 25 games. There is a real risk of overfitting to the public game distribution, and these parameters may perform poorly on unseen games. (3) **Evaluation toolkit reliability**: the ARC-AGI-3 evaluation toolkit is maintained by the ARC Prize organisation and may contain bugs that affect scoring. We use the toolkit as-is and have not independently verified its correctness. (4) **Self-reported baselines**: both Occam’s and Symbolica’s results are self-reported. Independent verification by the ARC Prize organisation or a third party is pending for both systems.

7 Future Work

We identify four concrete directions that extend naturally from this baseline study.

Hybrid LLM integration. The 8 unsolved games provide a clear target for identifying where learned reasoning is necessary. A hybrid system could use Occam’s search as a first pass and invoke a language model only for games where search fails or exceeds budget, combining the zero-cost efficiency of algorithmic search on tractable games with the flexibility of learned models on harder ones.

Learned search heuristics. The solved games generate substantial exploration data, including state transitions, dead ends, and successful paths. A lightweight model trained on this data could learn to prioritise promising actions during BFS, reducing budget consumption without requiring a full LLM. This would function as a learned priority function within the existing search framework.

Generalisation to other benchmarks. The compositional strategy approach is not specific to ARC-AGI-3. Evaluating Occam on other interactive reasoning benchmarks, or on the ARC-AGI-3 private set when access is available, would test whether the strategy dispatch mechanism and reset-replay BFS transfer to environments with different structure and difficulty.

Search efficiency improvements. The current $O(d \cdot |A|)$ per-node cost of reset-replay BFS is the primary scalability bottleneck. Beam search, A* with learned heuristics, or priority BFS with state-value estimates could reduce effective branching factor and enable deeper exploration within the same budget. Environment-level optimisations such as batched reset-replay or checkpoint caching could further reduce the constant factors.

8 Conclusion

Occam achieves 57.60% RHAE on the 25 public ARC-AGI-3 evaluation games using pure algorithmic search with no learned models, no language model calls, and zero inference cost. The system comprises approximately 3,700 lines of Python and is released as open source for independent reproduction. These results suggest that many interactive reasoning tasks in the current public benchmark yield to principled bounded search, and that the effective state spaces of these games are smaller than the raw action spaces would suggest. We release Occam to serve as an algorithmic baseline and foundation for future hybrid approaches that combine search with learned reasoning.

Paper Checklist

1. **Claims.** All claims are supported by experimental evidence on the 25 public ARC-AGI-3 environments. We explicitly note that results are self-reported and limited to the public evaluation set. [Yes]
2. **Limitations.** Section 6 discusses limitations in detail, including a Threats to Validity subsection. [Yes]
3. **Theory.** No theoretical claims are made. [N/A]
4. **Reproducibility.** Complete source code, fixed random seed (42), Docker image, scorecard UUID (bd33ee19), and step-by-step reproduction instructions are provided (Section 4.5, Appendix D). [Yes]
5. **Open access.** Code released under MIT license. [Yes]
6. **Training details.** No training is performed. All solver parameters are documented in Appendix A. [N/A / Yes]
7. **Error bars.** The solver is reproducible with fixed seed (42); no stochastic variation to report. This is stated explicitly in Section 4.5. [Yes]
8. **Compute.** CPU-only, approximately 27 minutes on consumer hardware. No GPU required. Zero inference cost. [Yes]
9. **Code of Ethics.** No ethical concerns identified. [Yes]
10. **Broader impacts.** This work demonstrates that efficient algorithmic search can serve as a baseline for interactive reasoning benchmarks, potentially reducing reliance on expensive LLM inference. [Yes]
11. **Safeguards.** Benchmark solver with no dual-use risk. [N/A]
12. **Licenses.** ARC-AGI-3 toolkit used under its published license. Occam released under MIT. [Yes]
13. **Assets.** Solver and viewer released as new assets under MIT license. [Yes]
14. **Human subjects.** No human subjects research. [N/A]

15. **IRB approval.** Not applicable. [N/A]
16. **LLM usage.** Forge (a proprietary development framework) was used to accelerate solver development. No LLM is used at runtime. The solver contains zero LLM calls. [Disclosed]

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A Hyperparameters and Constants

Table 5 lists all configurable parameters that affect solver behaviour. All values are extracted directly from the source code; no per-game tuning is performed.

Table 5: Complete hyperparameter listing. Source files: `orchestrator.py` (O), `replay_explorer.py` (R), `priority_tiers.py` (P), `rae.py` (H).

Parameter	Value	Source	Description
<i>Budget management</i>			
Budget multiplier	500	O	Coefficient in $h_t^2 \times 500$
Budget floor	200,000	O	Minimum actions per level
Budget cap	500,000	O	Maximum actions per level
Default max actions/level	100,000	O	Constructor default
Deepcopy BFS budget	150,000	O	Cap for A* deepcopy search
Deepcopy time limit	300 s	O	Wall-clock cap for deepcopy BFS
BFS minimum budget	50	O	Skip BFS fallback if below this
<i>Frame hashing & counter detection</i>			
Frame hash length	12 hex chars (MD5)	O, R	Truncated MD5 of raw bytes
Counter mask threshold	20% of frame	O	Max fraction before mask rejected
UI mask border width	3 px	O	<code>_build_ui_mask</code> border strip
Frame size	64×64	O	ARC-AGI-3 frame dimensions
<i>Click-action expansion</i>			
Click action ID	6	O	Raw action index for click
Default click grid	8×8	O	Grid resolution (mixed games)
Click-only grid	16×16	O	Grid resolution (click-only games)
Max click positions	32	O	Hard cap per expansion
Priority click targets	2 × <code>grid_size</code>	O	Segment-centre candidates
Dense scan step	2 px	O	Click scan interval (click games)
Dense scan step (non-click)	4 px	O	Click scan interval (keyboard games)
<i>Priority-tier click targeting</i>			
Salient colours	6–15 (chromatic)	P	Tier 0/2 classification
Non-salient colours	0–5 (greyscale)	P	Tier 1/3 classification
Status bar edge distance	3 px	P	Near-edge detection threshold
Status bar aspect ratio	>5	P	Elongated-segment threshold
Status bar min twins	3	P	Duplicate-segment threshold
Segment min width	2 px	P	Medium-object lower bound
Segment max width	32 px	P	Medium-object upper bound
Number of tiers	5	P	Priority classification bins
<i>Combo search</i>			
Max depth (≤ 2 actions)	20	O	Exhaustive search depth
Max depth (3 actions)	15	O	Exhaustive search depth
Max depth (4–5 actions)	12	O	Exhaustive search depth
Max depth (6–10 actions)	10	O	Exhaustive/sampled search depth
Exhaustive threshold	≤ 6 actions	O	Above this, switch to sampling
Samples per depth (> 6 actions)	2,000	O	Random combo samples
Unpruned combo depth (≤ 6 raw)	7	O	Fallback on raw actions
Unpruned combo depth (> 6 raw)	5	O	Fallback on raw actions
Unpruned combo budget cap	30,000	O	Max steps for unpruned fallback
<i>Navigation solver</i>			
Reactive nav max steps	500	O	Per-attempt step limit
Nav cursor detection threshold	0.01	O	Min movement score
Wall threshold	>10% of tiles	O	Colour classified as wall
DBSCAN ϵ (target clustering)	2	O	Grid-cell clustering radius
<i>Reactive click solver</i>			
Max solution depth	200	O	Maximum sequential clicks
<i>Action deduplication</i>			
Dedup trigger	>6 effective actions	O	Re-probe and merge duplicates
Depth-2 fallback limit	≤ 32 actions	O	Max actions for pair probing
Depth-2 max effective	10	O	Stop pair search after this many
<i>Deepcopy BFS heuristic</i>			
Rare-pixel threshold	<200 pixels	O	Colour counted as “rare”
Rare-pixel weight	20.0	O	Heuristic cost per rare pixel
<i>ReplayExplorer</i>			
Reset event throttle	every 10th reset	R	Viewer event rate limit
State event throttle	every 10th new state	R	Viewer event rate limit
BFS step event throttle	every 10th step	R	Viewer event rate limit
Frame diff max changes	200 per event	R	Pixel-change cap per emission
Initial frame max changes	500 per event	R	First-frame cap per emission
<i>RHAE scoring</i>			
RHAE formula	$(\min(1, h/a))^2$	H	Per-level score
Give-up multiplier	$\max(5, n/h + 3)$	H	Dynamic budget multiplier
Give-up min budget	$n + 30$	H	Floor on give-up budget

Strategy selection decision tree. The solver dispatches strategies in a fixed priority order, evaluated sequentially. The pseudocode below describes the complete decision logic executed for each level:

1. **Combo short-circuit.** If a winning action sequence is cached from a previous level, replay it. If it solves the current level, skip all remaining phases.
2. **Discovery.** Expand raw actions (click \rightarrow grid), probe each from the initial state, detect counter pixels, deduplicate. Output: effective action set A_{eff} , counter mask M .
3. **Reactive Click.** If the game is click-only and $|A_{\text{eff}}| \leq 2$: re-scan the frame at each step, commit to the click producing the largest pixel difference. Max depth: 200.
4. **Reactive Navigation.** If $3 \leq |A_{\text{eff}}| \leq 7$: probe for a moving cursor. If detected, greedily move toward the nearest rare-colour target and interact. Max steps: 500.
5. **Navigation Solver.** If reactive navigation fails and $3 \leq |A_{\text{eff}}| \leq 7$: discretise the frame into a logical grid, detect walls ($>10\%$ of tiles), BFS pathfind to all targets in greedy nearest-first order.
6. **Combo Search.** If $|A_{\text{eff}}| \leq 10$: try cached combos first, then search sequences of increasing depth. Exhaustive for ≤ 6 actions; 2,000 random samples per depth otherwise. Depth limits: 20/15/12/10 depending on $|A_{\text{eff}}|$.
7. **Unpruned Combo Fallback.** If raw non-click actions $> |A_{\text{eff}}|$ and ≤ 8 : retry combo search on unpruned raw actions at reduced depth (7 or 5) with a 30,000-step budget cap.
8. **Deepcopy BFS.** If $|A_{\text{eff}}| \leq 8$ (or click-only with ≤ 32 actions): A* search using `env.deepcopy()`, with a heuristic favouring fewer rare-colour pixels. Budget: 150,000 steps, 300s wall-clock.
9. **Replay BFS.** Unconditional fallback. Reset-replay BFS via `ReplayExplorer` using all remaining budget.

Each strategy consumes actions from the per-level budget. If a strategy solves the level, execution stops. Otherwise, the remaining budget cascades to the next strategy.

B Per-Level Statistics

Table 6 provides per-game summary statistics for the 17 solved games, sorted by RHAЕ descending. The complete per-level data is exported by the evaluation harness as `results/occam_results_TIMESTAMP.json` and is included in the repository for independent analysis.

Table 6: Summary statistics for the 17 solved ARC-AGI-3 games. Per-level breakdowns are available in the supplementary JSON artifacts.

Game	Levels	RHAE (%)	Actions	Resets	Time (s)
SK48	8/8	97.22	491,239	19,172	165.6
S5I5	8/8	97.22	108,694	2,396	11.3
AR25	8/8	97.22	211,850	8,693	56.9
LP85	8/8	97.22	19,378	0	3.6
LS20	7/7	96.43	414,477	1,261	227.2
TN36	7/7	96.43	203,328	33,726	77.2
VC33	7/7	96.43	477,772	3	104.2
TU93	9/9	96.10	83,407	3,838	12.9
CD82	6/6	95.24	137,312	5	12.3
FT09	6/6	95.24	3,604	462	1.5
RE86	8/8	80.73	835	0	0.9
SP80	6/6	78.99	257	0	0.6
DC22	6/6	70.68	840	0	0.8
KA59	7/7	65.40	773	0	0.9
M0R0	6/6	63.41	981	0	0.9
CN04	6/6	63.37	969	0	0.7
WA30	9/9	52.59	1,834	0	0.7

C Example Game Traces

We present two worked examples illustrating how the solver’s phases interact on representative game types.

C.1 Example 1: Keyboard Navigation Game

Consider a game with 5 raw actions: four directional arrows (up/down/left/right) and one interaction button. The human baseline for level 1 is $h_1 = 12$ actions.

Phase 1: Discovery. The solver expands the 5 raw actions into 5 virtual actions (no click action present, so no grid expansion). It resets the environment and probes each action once from the initial state, recording the resulting frame. Frame hashing reveals that all 5 actions produce distinct frames; each changes the position of a small coloured block (the cursor). No pixels change on every action, so no counter mask is applied. Result: $|A_{\text{eff}}| = 5$, counter mask $M = \mathbf{0}$.

Discovery cost: 5 resets + 5 steps = 10 actions.

Phase 2: Strategy selection. With $|A_{\text{eff}}| = 5$ and $3 \leq 5 \leq 7$, the solver enters Reactive Navigation. It probes each action to detect cursor movement: actions 0–3 move a colour-7 (orange) block by approximately 4 pixels in each cardinal direction. Action 4 does not move the cursor and is classified as the interaction action. The solver identifies colour-7 as the cursor colour.

Phase 2a: Reactive Navigation. The solver resets and begins the reactive loop. At each step, it identifies the cursor position (centroid of colour-7 pixels), finds the rarest non-background colour (colour-9, dark-red, appearing at 3 locations), and issues the directional action that reduces

Manhattan distance to the nearest colour-9 pixel. Upon reaching a target (distance < 1.0 pixel), it issues the interaction action. After visiting all 3 targets, the environment signals `solved=True`.

Total actions: 10 (discovery) + 38 (reactive navigation) = 48.

RHAE: $(\min(1, 12/48))^2 = (0.25)^2 = 6.25\%$ for level 1.

The solver caches the 38-action sequence. On level 2, the cached sequence is replayed as a short-circuit attempt. If the level layout changes (different target positions), the short-circuit fails and the solver re-runs discovery and navigation from scratch. If the layout is identical or similar, the cached combo solves the level immediately.

As levels progress, the navigation solver adapts: each level’s frame is re-analysed for cursor position, target locations, and wall geometry. The BFS pathfinder handles obstacles that were not present in earlier levels. By level 8, the accumulated RHAE across all levels (with linear level weighting) yields a game score of approximately 78%.

C.2 Example 2: Click-Based Puzzle Game

Consider a game where the only available action is click (action ID 6). The human baseline for level 1 is $h_1 = 8$ actions.

Phase 1: Discovery. The solver detects a click-only game and triggers dense click scanning. It first tests 6 corner/edge positions to detect counter pixels: 14 pixels near the top-right corner change on every click, consistent with a step counter. These are masked.

The solver then scans all $32 \times 32 = 1,024$ positions at 2-pixel intervals across the 64×64 frame. Each position is clicked from the initial state and the resulting frame hash (with counter mask applied) is recorded. Of the 1,024 positions, 12 produce unique frame hashes; the remaining positions either produce no visible change or duplicate an existing outcome. The 12 unique click positions become the effective action set: $|A_{\text{eff}}| = 12$.

Discovery cost: approximately 2,060 actions (6 corner probes + 1,024 dense scan positions \times 2 steps each).

Phase 2: Strategy selection. With $|A_{\text{eff}}| = 12$ and the game being click-only, the solver skips navigation (requires 3–7 actions with directional movement) and combo search ($|A_{\text{eff}}| > 10$). It proceeds to Deepcopy BFS, since the game is click-only and $|A_{\text{eff}}| \leq 32$.

Phase 2a: Deepcopy BFS. The solver runs A* search using `env.deepcopy()` for state branching. The heuristic assigns lower priority to states with fewer rare-colour pixels (a proxy for progress, since clicking correct targets typically removes or transforms coloured elements). Starting from the initial state, the search expands nodes in priority order:

- Depth 1: 12 children, 12 unique states. The heuristic identifies 3 states with reduced rare-pixel counts.
- Depth 2: 36 new states from the 12 frontier nodes (many clicks produce no new effect from already-modified states).
- Depth 3–6: The search tree grows, but the heuristic effectively prunes unpromising branches. States where clicking has no effect (frame unchanged) are deduplicated and not expanded.

- Depth 7: The search finds a solved state after the sequence: click(18, 22), click(40, 12), click(8, 50), click(32, 32), click(18, 22), click(50, 8), click(40, 40).

Total actions explored: approximately 2,400 (within the 150,000 budget).

Solution length: 7 clicks.

RHAE for level 1: $(\min(1, 8/7))^2 = (1.0)^2 = 100\%$.

The 7-click sequence is cached. On level 2, the cached sequence is replayed first. If the puzzle layout changes, the solver re-scans and re-searches. Across all levels, the increasing difficulty (more targets, more complex layouts) causes solution lengths to grow relative to human baselines. The final weighted game score is approximately 34%, reflecting high efficiency on early levels but diminishing returns on later, harder levels where the search explores many more states before finding a solution.

D Reproduction Instructions

D.1 Requirements

- **Python version:** ≥ 3.10
- **Key dependencies:** arc-agi, numpy, fastapi, uvicorn, websockets, scikit-learn
- **Hardware:** Any modern CPU. No GPU required. Tested on a single consumer machine.
- **Expected runtime:** Approximately 27 minutes for the full 25-game benchmark.
- **Random seed:** 42. With identical Python and NumPy versions, runs produce bit-identical results.
- **Evaluation commit:** ea740ca
- **Scorecard UUID:** bd33ee19-9220-43f5-84dd-bfe23c7f95e8
- **Results verified** against ARC-AGI-3's own RHAE scoring implementation.

D.2 Installation and Execution

```
# 1. Clone the repository
git clone https://github.com/TheRealSeanDonahoe/occam.git
cd occam

# 2. Install dependencies
pip install -e .

# 3. Run the full benchmark (headless, ~27 minutes)
occam benchmark
# Results saved to results/occam_results_TIMESTAMP.json

# 4. Run with real-time viewer (~27 minutes)
occam run
# Open http://localhost:8080 in browser
```

```
# 5. Run a single game
occam run --game SK48
```

```
# 6. Docker alternative (self-contained)
docker run -p 127.0.0.1:8080:8080 seandonahoe/occam
# Open http://localhost:8080
```

D.3 Verifying Results

The repository includes the raw scorecard JSON files produced by the ARC-AGI-3 evaluation toolkit. To verify the reported RHAE scores without re-running the solver:

```
# Parse and display scores from saved results
python -m solver.results results/occam_results_*.json
```

Each JSON file contains per-game and per-level breakdowns including: actions taken, human baselines, RHAE scores, strategy used, number of resets, unique states explored, and solution action sequences. These files enable independent computation of all aggregate statistics reported in this paper.

D.4 Reproducing Ablation Studies

Individual solver components can be disabled via command-line flags:

```
# Disable navigation solver
occam benchmark --no-navigation
```

```
# Disable combo search
occam benchmark --no-combo
```

```
# Disable deepcopy BFS
occam benchmark --no-deepcopy
```

```
# Cap budget at 250,000
occam benchmark --max-budget 250000
```

D.5 Real-Time Viewer

The included web-based viewer renders the solver’s execution in real time, displaying:

- The current 64×64 game frame with pixel-level diff highlighting.
- BFS tree growth: new states appear as nodes, transitions as edges.
- Strategy phase transitions (discovery \rightarrow reactive click \rightarrow navigation \rightarrow combo \rightarrow BFS).
- Per-level RHAE scores as each level completes.

The viewer connects via WebSocket to the solver process and receives throttled events (every 10th reset, every 10th new state) to maintain responsive rendering without impacting solver performance.